

Organizational Culture, Information Technology Use and Evidence-Based Practice among Librarians in Universities in South-West, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://10.5281/zenodo.11110618>

Abstract

This paper is a report of a study examining organizational culture, information technology use and evidence-based practice of librarians in universities in South-West, Nigeria. Evidence-based practice is a complementary mechanism that helps librarians in the problem-solving and decision-making process. This concept gives additional value to many aspects of library activities and services. In spite of the immense benefits of evidence-based practice, researchers have observed the involvement of librarians in evidence-based practice is low. University library management has been challenged to foster, sustain and improve on the level of organizational culture and information technology use of librarians so as to enhance evidence-based practice. A survey research design was used for the study, with 226 professional librarians in 19 universities in South-West, Nigeria. Total enumeration was used. A structured and validated questionnaire was used to collect data. Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients for the constructs ranged from 0.86 to 0.94. A response rate of 77.8% was achieved. Data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential (simple and multiple regression) statistics at 5% level of significance. Findings showed that organizational culture and information technology use have combined significant influence on evidence-based practice. Organizational culture and information technology use enhanced evidence-based practice of librarians in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria. This study recommended that university library management should sustain and improve the level of organizational culture and information technology use of librarians to enhance evidence-based practice.

Keywords: Evidence-based librarianship, Evidence-based practice, Information technology use, Organizational culture, Professional librarians.

Introduction

Evidence-based practice is applying or translating research findings in our daily practice to make good decisions regarding professional practice. The concept of evidence-based practice originated in medicine in the early 1990s. Known as Evidence-Based Medicine (EBM), EBM anchors on merging what is learned from the literature with what is observed in daily practice to produce a better result that can be used to inform medical practice. Since then, the movement has extended to other fields of knowledge such as nursing, rehabilitation and even librarianship. In Library and Information Science, Evidence-Based Practice (EBP) is also known as Evidence-Based Library Practice (EBLIP). EBP involves a method of resolving daily problems in the library profession through the integration of experience and research. It involves asking questions, finding evidence to answer the questions and applying that knowledge to library practice. Evidence-based practice supports librarians in problem-solving and decision-making processes.

The librarians' experience in applying EBP was reported by Asrat *et al.* (2021) who developed a model to capture the critical variation of librarians' experiences at applying formal research skills and methods to assist in decision-making and establish best practice. The main concern of EBP in decision-making is to find tools that support the processes (Brian, 2016) and the librarians' readiness to implement them (Aliyu, 2016 in Mustapha & Noorhidawati, 2020). There are numerous kinds of evidence used by librarians and various evidence sources that libraries can refer to in engaging library practice with evidence-based activities. The type of evidence used depends on the librarians' needs. When a librarian understands which evidence is the best for the context of the problem, they will seek deeper information and build knowledge on that matter. Incorporating evidence-based practice into library activities has been found not only useful in better decision-making that saves the time of the library users but also fosters lifelong learning and critical thinking (Andrea, 2020), there is therefore the need for the involvement of librarians. Which could be associated or linked to organizational culture and information technology use in the workspace.

Statement of the Problem

Effective library practice entails that decisions on library practice are taken in an evidence-based manner, because such decisions will not only help to improve the quality of decision-making and skills of librarians in literature searching but will also increase the ability of

librarians to scientifically support decision or action. However, researchers have observed that the active engagement of librarians in evidence-based library practice is low. This low rate of evidence-based library practice is shown in the librarians' low research and publications rate (Penta & McKenzie, 2005) too old, library being deficient in hard evidence (Taylor, et al., 2015), low participation of librarians in evidence-based initiatives, and a misconception that evidence-based practice is solely meant for medical librarians. While these factors have been attributed to the low rate of evidence-based practice, there may be other factors such as organizational culture and information technology use that could influence evidence-based practice. Organizational culture, an integral part of the library system, when properly managed, could enhance the implementation of EBP, enhance positive attitude of librarians towards EBP, and also moderate the use of evidence results. Information Technology (IT), on the other hand, is a crucial element in evidence-based practice if properly harnessed, will not only enhance librarians' access to information for evidence-based practice but also can serve as veritable tools to teach, capture, transfer and maintain data for evidence-based practice.

From the above, therefore, the ideal situation should be that decisions regarding library practice should be based on scientific pieces of evidence, the engagement of librarians that are supposed to initiate these decisions in an evidence-based approach is low. Hence, this research work stands to look at how organizational culture and information technology use could enhance the implementation of evidence-based practice among librarians in universities in South West, Nigeria. Past research studies have looked at various aspects of EBP of librarians but failed to examine how organizational culture and information technology use influence EBP of librarians in South-West university libraries in Nigeria. This constitutes a gap to be filled in this study. Therefore, this study investigated the influence of organizational culture and information technology use on evidence-based practice among librarians in universities in South-West, Nigeria.

Research objectives are to:

1. Determine the level of evidence-based practice of librarians in the university libraries in South-West, Nigeria;
2. Find out the dimensions of organizational culture in the university libraries in South-West, Nigeria;
3. Find out the Information Technology use of the librarians in University libraries in South-West, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study is a descriptive research method with a questionnaire as the instrument of data collection. A total enumeration sampling technique was adopted to sample two hundred and twenty-six (226) librarians (respondents) in nineteen public universities across the South-West, of Nigeria. Indicate the method used in analyzing the data collected for the study.

Literature Review

Evidence-Based Practice

Clack and Alisa (2020), defined evidence-based practice as an approach to professional practice that involves a structured process of collecting, interpreting and applying valid and reliable research findings and evidence to support decision-making to enhance continuous service improvement in professional practice Eric, *et al.* (2014) defined it as the process of making a good-quality decision based on a combination of critical thinking and the best available evidence These definitions, therefore, suggest that librarians as information providers need to possess a high level of skill in thinking and understanding to correctly isolate relevant contextual issues that influence utilization of research evidence for decision making (Chiwuala, 2018), as well as necessary expertise and experiences. Expertise in LIS has to do with the integration of accumulated knowledge, librarianship experiences; information from education and librarianship skills in making decisions. Librarians must also possess research skills to be able to identify a central issue from the findings, then summarize and combine relevant research findings from different studies into one idea that can be interpreted in order to make sense of current available evidence. Incorporating users' value preferences in decision-making entails a user-centred approach where users' views, opinions, beliefs, priorities and expectations are included in the decision-making process. All these will help the librarian to produce a plan of service that is best for library users

Organizational Culture

Organizational culture has been operationalized in many different ways in the research literature. Schneider, *et al.* (2017) defined organizational culture as the shared values and basic assumptions explaining why organisations do what they do and focus on what they focus on.

Based on these definitions, culture stands to perform two important roles in organization; (1) to integrate members so as to have a collective identity that enables them to work together and (2) to help organization so as to be able to adapt to environmental changes, such as meeting its goals and relate with outsiders. In sum, organizational culture therefore is something that can be learnt from experience, and taught to others (Edwinah, 2014). Organizational culture is what differentiates one organization from the other. Organizational culture performs a number of roles as noticed by extant research literature. First, it allows employees to share creative ideas, differentiates one organization from another, gives a sense of identity to corporate members, enhances the generation of commitment to the organization, it is a crucial factor in enhancing organizational effectiveness (Samreen Hazril and Ahmad, 2024) Maartje and JoZef (2020), opined that organizational culture improves and increases employees' job satisfaction, shapes employee response to incivility (Balaji, Gurbir and Subhash, 20 employee's performance (Maryati, Happy, and Rohana (2020).

Information Technology Use

Information technology refers to computing technologies, such as networking, hardware, software, the internet or the people that work with these technologies for receiving, storing, processing, transmitting and presentation of information (Zahra et al., 2016). According to him, IT includes radios, scanners, modems, mice, screens, printers, handsets, television, word processing and operating system software, etc. Computer provides the processing, storage and retrieval facilities while telecommunications provides the facilities for transferring the information to those that need it. The advent of IT has improved efficiency in the performance of routine tasks in the library and many other aspects of the economy such education, health, political and social aspects as observed by Rawwary et al. (2020). As managers oversee resource coordination and allocation, it can be difficult to coordinate organizational activities across various projects; information technology is one of the key innovations that is frequently implemented to assist in this process. Ade (2020), opined that IT is used to facilitate communication, achieve organizational goals, improve integration, and enhance productivity and service delivery. In academic libraries, IT helps to improve the efficiency of library services, global integration of library services, universal access to information, digitalization of documents for preservation, space-saving and has also encouraged networking and global resource sharing (Adeleke, et al. 2014).

Despite the benefits of IT use in organizations, users' resistance to its use has been identified as a salient reason for the failure of its adoption. Scholars attest to the fact that people have developed a resistance toward the use of IT in accessing information. Nazire and Ugur, (2020), attributed the failure of the adoption of IT to users' resistance. Users' resistance is an adverse reaction or the opposition of users to perceived change related to a new information system implementation. This resistance according to Bahae (2018) coupled with little incentive to use IT has posed a major difficulty that persists among many professionals. Therefore, it is important for librarians to understand the reason for resistance and find a solution, and manage it (Lapointe, 2012). Nazire and Ugur (2020), outlined these factors that has caused the resistance as: culture, technological, and hierarchical. In the opinion of Oluwole (2016), it is the fear of the feeling of anxiety connected with the introduction of information technology. Amit, *et al.*, (2020), therefore suggested that organization has to go through system development life cycle such as feasibility study, system analysis, system design, system implementation integration and testing and system audit to be able optimized the use of information technology. Information technology use will be examined under the following dimensions.

Findings and Discussions

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the level of evidence-based practice of librarians in the universities in South-West, Nigeria?

Evidence-based Practice of librarians

Evidence-Based Practice	Very high level (4)	High level (3)	Low level (2)	Very low level (1)	Mean	Std.
Knowledge					3.45	0.537
My knowledge and awareness of major information types and sources is	98 (55.7%)	77 (43.8%)	0	1 (0.6%)	3.55	0.533
My knowledge of how to retrieve evidence is	83 (47.2%)	92 (52.3%)	1 (0.6%)	0	3.47	0.512
My knowledge in applying evidence is	81 (46.0%)	92 (52.3%)	3 (1.7%)	0	3.44	0.531

My knowledge of how to appraise evidence is	78 (44.3%)	95 (54.0%)	3 (1.7%)	0	3.43	0.529
My level of information sharing with colleagues is	83 (47.2%)	86 (48.9%)	7 (4.0%)	0	3.43	0.572
My level of evaluation of the outcome of my practice is	76 (43.2%)	95 (54.0%)	5 (2.8%)	0	3.40	0.547
Skills					3.40	0.574
The level of my ability to identify information sources is	101 (57.4%)	70 (39.8%)	4 (2.3%)	1 (0.6%)	3.54	0.574
The level of my ability to retrieve evidence is	82 (46.6%)	87 (49.4%)	7 (4.0%)	0	3.43	0.571
The level of my skill in applying the evidence is	73 (41.5%)	96 (54.5%)	7 (4.0%)	0	3.38	0.562
The level of skill in sharing the ideas and information with my other colleagues is	73 (41.5%)	96 (54.5%)	5 (2.8%)	2 (1.1%)	3.36	0.599
The level of my skill in evaluating my performance is	70 (39.8%)	98 (55.7%)	7 (4.0%)	1 (0.6%)	3.35	0.585
The level of my ability to determine how valid (close to the truth) the evidence is	65 (36.9%)	104 (59.1%)	7 (4.0%)	0	3.33	0.550
Practice					3.32	0.599
My competency in evaluating the outcome of my practice is	77 (43.8%)	88 (50.0%)	9 (5.1%)	2 (1.1%)	3.36	0.636
My competency in retrieving evidence once i have formulated the question is	70 (39.8%)	95 (54.0%)	11 (6.3%)	0	3.34	0.591
The level of my ability to apply the evidence retrieved to inform my practice is	71 (40.3%)	95 (54.0%)	9 (5.1%)	1 (0.6%)	3.34	0.603
The level of my ability in sharing the evidence retrieved with other librarians is	69 (39.2%)	97 (55.1%)	8 (4.5%)	2 (1.1%)	3.32	0.617
The level of my ability in formulating answerable question at the beginning so as to fill the gap in practice is	61 (34.7%)	106 (60.2%)	9 (5.1%)	0	3.30	0.559

My capability to critically appraise the worthiness of the evidence that has been retrieved is	61 (34.7%)	102 (58.5%)	13 (7.4%)	0	3.27	0.590
Grand Mean					3.39	0.570

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2023

Decision rule: 1. 0 – 1.74 = Very low; 1.75 – 2.49 = Low; 2.5 – 3.24 = High, 3.25 – 4.0 = Very high.

Librarians were asked to indicate their level of evidence-based practice in South-West, Nigeria in Table 4.2. The result indicates high level of evidence-based practice of librarians in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria ($\bar{x} = 3.39$, $SD = 0.570$), on a scale of 4. Evidence-based practice was divided into three dimensions namely knowledge, skills and practice. The average mean values for each of the evidence-based practice constructs were also calculated. Of the three dimensions of evidence-based practice measured, knowledge was rated the highest ($\bar{x} = 3.45$) while practice had the lowest rating ($\bar{x} = 3.32$) among the librarians.

This situation could be because librarians in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria are knowledgeable in major information types and sources, and also are highly skilled in identifying information sources. These results suggest the need for librarians in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria to sustain performance in the process of using research results and other valid data in decision-making in library practice.

Research Question Two: What is the dimension of organizational culture in university libraries in South-West Nigerian universities?

Organizational Culture of librarians

Organizational Culture	Strongly agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly disagree (1)	Mean	Std.
Mission					3.51	0.568
I know the purpose of the existence of the organization	114 (64.8%)	60 (34.1%)	2 (1.1%)	0	3.63	0.552
My performance is always toward the organizational vision	111 (63.1%)	62 (35.2%)	2 (1.1%)	1 (0.6%)	3.61	0.545
I know the goals and objectives of the organization	110 (62.5%)	64 (36.4%)	1 (0.6%)	1 (0.6%)	3.61	0.534

My organization clearly communicate vision	92 (52.3%)	79 (44.9%)	3 (1.7%)	2 (1.1%)	3.48	0.595
I know the major priorities of the organization	77 (43.8%)	93 (52.8%)	5 (2.8%)	1 (0.6%)	3.40	0.576
I know the long term plan of the organization	74 (42.0%)	90 (51.1%)	12 (6.8%)	0	3.35	0.605
Involvement					3.47	0.579
I value collaboration and feel mutually accountable for common goal	106 (60.2%)	67 (38.1%)	3 (1.7%)	0	3.59	0.528
Teamwork is encouraged in the organization	97 (55.1%)	68 (38.6%)	11 (6.3%)	0	3.49	0.614
I develop my skills	88 (50.0%)	84 (47.7%)	4 (2.3%)	0	3.48	0.545
Decisions are taken based on enough information	91 (51.7%)	74 (42.0%)	10 (5.7%)	1 (0.6%)	3.45	0.630
I develop my ability as an important source for the organization's competitiveness	82 (46.6%)	90 (51.1%)	2 (1.1%)	2 (1.1%)	3.43	0.585
I involve in information sharing to the employees	74 (42.0%)	94 (53.4%)	8 (4.5%)	0	3.38	0.572
Consistency					3.34	0.589
I reconcile differences with other employees in a constructive way when problem arises	87 (49.4%)	87 (49.4%)	1 (0.6%)	1 (0.6%)	3.48	0.545
My organization is able to reach an agreement on critical issues	78 (44.3%)	90 (51.1%)	7 (4.0%)	1 (0.6%)	3.39	0.595
I share a set of value that create a strong sense of identity	65 (36.9%)	106 (60.2%)	3 (1.7%)	2 (1.1%)	3.33	0.570
Employees from different units share information	68 (38.6%)	95 (54.0%)	11 (6.3%)	2 (1.1%)	3.30	0.637
Work activity is easy to perform in the organization	63 (35.8%)	100 (56.8%)	13 (7.4%)	0	3.28	0.594
My leaders model reinforces the shared values	61 (34.7%)	102 (58.0%)	13 (7.4%)	0	3.27	0.590
Adaptability					3.31	0.598

I constantly look for a new way of doing things	80 (45.5%)	93 (52.8%)	2 (1.1%)	1 (0.6%)	3.43	0.551
I respond to organization users changing needs	74 (42.0%)	99 (56.3%)	3 (1.7%)	0	3.40	0.526
I study the external environment and change accordingly.	74 (42.0%)	96 (54.5%)	4 (2.3%)	2 (1.1%)	3.38	0.592
Knowledge is shared across my organization	71 (40.3%)	93 (52.7%)	12 (6.8%)	0	3.34	0.601
I understand the needs of organization members	57 (32.4%)	111 (63.1%)	7 (4.0%)	1 (0.6%)	3.27	0.560
Failure is applied as consideration to a better direction	43 (24.4%)	103 (58.5%)	21 (11.9%)	9 (5.1%)	3.02	0.756
Grand Mean					3.41	0.584

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2023

Decision rule: 1.0 – 1.74 = Strongly disagree; 1.75 – 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50 – 3.24 = Agree; 3.25 – 4.0 = Strongly agree.

Table 4.3 indicates that participants agreed that there was organizational culture among librarians in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria ($\bar{x} = 3.41$, $SD = 0.584$). Librarians specifically agreed that the dimensions of organizational culture in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria were as follows: mission ($\bar{x} = 3.51$), involvement ($\bar{x} = 3.47$), consistency ($\bar{x} = 3.34$), adaptability ($\bar{x} = 3.31$). However, the organizational culture indicator that was rated to be prominent among librarians in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria is the culture of mission ($\bar{x} = 3.51$). Under mission, the respondents indicated that they know the purpose of the organization with the highest mean score rating of ($\bar{x} = 3.63$). However, knowledge of the long-term plan of the organization had the lowest rating under mission culture with a mean score of $\bar{x} = 3.35$.

Furthermore, following the culture of mission is involvement ($\bar{x} = 3.47$). In the involvement culture, librarians responded by rating that they value collaboration and feel mutually accountable for common goal in the library ($\bar{x} = 3.59$). They also noted that teamwork is encouraged in the organization ($\bar{x} = 3.49$). However, involvement in information sharing to employees was rated the lowest under the culture of involvement ($\bar{x} = 3.38$). Following involvement is consistency ($\bar{x} = 3.34$) in which librarians noted that they reconcile differences with other employees in a constructive way when problem arises ($\bar{x} = 3.48$) and their organization is able to reach an agreement on critical issues ($\bar{x} = 3.39$). The culture that is

ranked lowest is the adaptability culture ($\bar{x} = 3.31$) which librarians agreed that they constantly look for a new way of doing things ($\bar{x} = 3.43$). The implication of this result is that in the university libraries in South-West, Nigeria, there seems to be a strong culture based on the prevailing indicators of mission, involvement, consistency and adaptability.

Research Question Three: What is the information technology use of librarians in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria?

Table 4.4

Information Technology Use of Librarians

IT tools used	Strongly agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly disagree (1)	Mean	Std.
Purpose of use					3.63	0.565
For better library practice	137 (77.8%)	36 (20.5%)	2 (1.1%)	1 (0.6%)	3.76	0.493
To meet up with the IT Age Demand	127 (72.2%)	49 (27.8%)	0	0	3.72	0.449
Operational efficiency	129 (73.3%)	41 (23.3%)	5 (2.8%)	1 (0.6%)	3.69	0.553
Flexibility of information search	117 (66.5%)	56 (31.8%)	2 (1.1%)	1 (0.6%)	3.64	0.537
Accuracy of library services	114 (64.8%)	57 (32.4%)	5 (2.8%)	0	3.62	0.542
Error-free services	95 (54.0%)	57 (32.4%)	17 (9.7%)	7 (4.0%)	3.36	0.817
Type of IT tools used					3.59	0.605
Computer	153 (86.9%)	22 (12.5%)	0	1 (0.6%)	3.86	0.396
Electronic database	127 (72.2%)	46 (26.1%)	2 (1.1%)	1 (0.6%)	3.70	0.518
Smartphone	120 (68.2%)	52 (29.5%)	3 (1.7%)	1 (0.6%)	3.65	0.544
Scanner	121 (68.8%)	47 (26.7%)	7 (4.0%)	1 (0.6%)	3.64	0.589
Multiple Projector	90 (51.1%)	65 (36.9%)	17 (9.7%)	4 (2.3%)	3.37	0.752

Camera	89 (50.6%)	59 (33.5%)	21 (11.9%)	7 (4.0%)	3.31	0.833
	Very high extent (4)	High extent (3)	Low extent (2)	Very low extent (1)	Mean	Std.
Extent of use					3.40	0.714
Computer	139 (79.0%)	36 (20.5%)	1 (0.6%)	0	3.78	0.426
Smartphone	113 (64.2%)	54 (30.7%)	6 (3.4%)	3 (1.7%)	3.57	0.646
Network	112 (63.6%)	49 (27.8%)	13 (7.4%)	2 (1.1%)	3.54	0.683
Scanner	83 (47.2%)	64 (36.4%)	25 (14.2%)	4 (2.3%)	3.28	0.792
Projector	72 (40.9%)	65 (36.9%)	33 (18.8%)	6 (3.4%)	3.15	0.845
Camera	64 (36.4%)	67 (38.1%)	35 (19.9%)	10 (5.7%)	3.05	0.890
Grand Mean					3.54	0.628

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2023

Decision rule: 1.0- 1.74 = Strongly disagree and very low extent; 1.75 – 2.49 = Disagree and Low level; 2.50 – 3.24 = Agree and High extent; 3.25 – 4.0 = Strongly agree and Very High extent

Table 4.4 reveals that information technology use has a very high usage in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria ($\bar{x} = 3.54$, $SD = 0.628$). Some of the information technology used in university libraries include computers ($\bar{x} = 3.86$), electronic databases ($\bar{x} = 3.70$) and smartphone ($\bar{x} = 3.65$). Table 4.4 also reveals that computer ($\bar{x} = 3.78$) and smartphone ($\bar{x} = 3.57$) were used to a very high extent. The purpose of information technology use was also presented in Table 4.4. For better library practice was rated the highest with a mean score of ($\bar{x} = 3.76$), while error-free services was rated the lowest ($\bar{x} = 3.36$).

Discussing of Findings

The study looked at organizational culture and information technology use and evidence-based practice of librarians in universities in South-West, Nigeria. This section deals with detailed findings of the study and discusses the findings in conjunction with previous research studies

used in the work. The research questions and hypotheses drawn for the study were intended at examining organizational culture, information technology use and evidence-based practice of librarians in universities in South-West, Nigeria.

Research Question 1: What is the level of evidence-based practice of librarians in the universities in South-West, Nigeria?

Research question one sought to find out the level of evidence-based practice of librarians in the universities in South-West, Nigeria. The findings shown high level of evidence-based practice of librarians in university libraries in South-West Nigeria. Participants agreed that knowledge, skill and practice were involved in evidence-based practice uptake. The findings are in line with theory of knowing in practice of Ryle, (1945) which opined that knowledge, skill and practice are the three prominent indicators that can be used to measure practice. However, the evidence-based practice indicator that was rated highest among librarians is knowledge. Under knowledge, the librarians agreed that they have the awareness of major information types and sources with the mean score of 3.55. This finding is in agreement with Aliyu's, (2016) and Alshehri, *et al.* (2018) studies that affirmed that librarians are relatively knowledgeable about evidence-based practice and skilled in identifying appropriate resources for evidence-based practice also that librarians can identify and retrieve evidence from literature and from various sources. The finding also indicated that librarians have the knowledge of how to retrieve evidence. The finding confirmed Ida *et al.* (2017) that revealed that librarians can retrieve evidence and use them for various purposes. Librarians agreed that they have the knowledge in applying evidence. The finding also affirmed Jennifer's (2014), Luo's (2018) and Howlet and Howard's (2015) studies that revealed that librarians involved themselves in some form of EBP activities such as informally collect evidence from stakeholders, use evidence to impact knowledge and also use social circle network to access evidence that can support their information needs. In addition to the findings, librarians agreed that they are knowledgeable at appraising evidence. The finding agreed with Deborah and Kathryn's (2023) study which submitted that librarians prepare evidence summaries, provide searching services and also help individuals to build critical appraisal skills so as to assess the increasing amount of information. In addition, librarians have the knowledge of sharing information with colleagues and evaluation of the outcome of their practice. This finding is in line with Wan, *et al.* (2018) study that affirmed that librarians evaluate the outcome of their practice and that such practice has helped the librarians to construct its library strategic plan which has positively enhanced the library management system.

In addition to the findings, librarians agreed that they have a high-level skill at identifying information sources, retrieving evidence, critical appraisal, applying evidence, sharing of evidence, and evaluating performance. This finding agreed with Maryam, et al. (2021), studies that revealed that librarians must be familiar with various evidence sources, skillful in resource selection and possess skill for effective communication, Ida et al. (2017), study that revealed that librarians need to have a good evidence based skill in literature searching; as well as Susan's and Nasra's (2021) study that revealed that librarians must possess a complex set of skill that requires him to critically evaluate relevant research literature.

Furthermore, the finding revealed that librarians indicated their involvement in the practice of Evidence-Based Practice with formulating answerable question at the beginning so as to fill the gap in practice. competency in retrieving evidence once the question has been formulated, capability to critically appraise the worthiness of the evidence that has been retrieved, ability to apply the evidence retrieved to inform their practice, ability to share the evidence retrieved with other librarians, and competency in evaluating the outcome of their practice, ($\bar{x} = 3.36$). These findings supported the positions of Ida *et al.* (2017), Luo, (2018), Annie and Zvezdana (2014), which revealed that librarians involved themselves in evidence-based activities such as supporting evidence-based practice, searching for evidence from different sources, engaging in critical appraisal of evidence, applying various types of pieces of evidence to inform practice, sharing the pieces of evidence and evaluating the outcome of the intervention. This result suggests the need for librarians in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria to sustain their performance in the process of using research results, data, and other valid evidences in decision-making in library practice.

Research Question 2: What is the dimension of organizational culture in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria?

Research question two sought to find out the dimension of organizational culture in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria. The findings showed that participants agreed that there was organizational culture among in the libraries. Librarians also specifically agreed that the dimensions of organizational culture in the libraries are mission, involvement, consistency and adaptability. The findings are in line with Denison's organizational culture model with cultural index of four dimensions (mission, involvement, consistency and adaptability), which

emphasized the important characteristics that an organization should possess to perform maximally.

However, the organizational culture indicator that was rated to be prominent among librarians in the university libraries was a mission. Under the mission, the respondents indicated that they know the purpose of setting up the organization. Also, that they have the knowledge of the long-term plan of the organization with lowest rating under mission culture. Mission was rated high probably because the respondents believed that mission is the most important aspect of the organization that provides the opportunity to make clear to employees what the organization values. This finding confirmed Alfatat and Mohammed's (2020), and Isabel *et al.* (2015) studies which revealed that mission is important because it offers directions, defines the scope, promotes shared values among organizational members, promotes and motivates the interest of external members of the organization. The finding affirmed Choon and Patrick's (2016) whose study outcome revealed that having a good mission statement in organization has a significant relationship with employee effectiveness.

Furthermore, following the culture of mission is involvement, where respondents agreed that they value collaboration and are mutually accountable for common goal in the library. The findings are in line with Denison cultural model (1999) which submitted that inculcating the culture of involvement and collaboration among employees can lead to the success of the organization. The finding also corroborated the assertion of Jackline and Ezekiel (2018), whose study findings affirmed that involvement was strongly and positively correlated to employees' performance. In addition, the findings also showed that the participants agreed that, teamwork is encouraged. This finding agreed with Kelemba, *et al.* (2017) study which affirmed that teamwork ensures democracy at work place, enhances changes and encourages innovation. Participants also agreed that they developed their skills, and that decisions are taken based on sufficient information. Also they agreed that they develop their ability as an important source for the organization's competitiveness. This finding confirmed the finding of Nanita's (2020) study that opined that librarians developed their skills so as to be able to face the challenges that occur due to the changing environment. Participants also agreed that they are involved in information sharing to the employees. The finding is in line with Awa and Kalu's (2017), and Tomi, Jibril, and Babalola's (2020) studies which revealed that academic librarians are involved in resource sharing, and that such information sharing enhances strategic partnership in organizations.

Following involvement is consistency, in which librarians noted that they reconciled differences with other employees in constructive ways when problems arise, and their organization is able to reach an agreement on critical issues. The librarians also agreed that they share a set of values that create a strong sense of identity, work activity is easy to perform, and leaders' model reinforces the shared values. These findings affirmed the findings of Fabrizia, Chiara, and Maria's (2015), and Manuel's (2020), studies which opined that harmonious industrial relations are indeed the most important remedy for organization suffering from poor management and that customer relations management improves organizational performance.

The culture that is ranked lowest is the adaptability culture, in which librarians agree that they constantly look for a new way of doing things. This finding confirmed Horth and Vekar's (2014) studies which revealed that a new way of doing things (innovation) in organizations, is paramount to the organization because innovation ensures the survival, success and continuity of an organization. In addition, implementing something new also adds value or quantifiable gain. Librarians also agreed that they respond to organization users' changing needs. This finding is in agreement with Horsfaff (2023) who submitted that librarians need to respond to change so as to meet the needs of the ever-changing library users, and because of the competition in the information sector.

Librarians also agreed that they study the external environment and change accordingly, this finding is in line with Momoh, and Folorunso's (2019) study which revealed that librarians must adapt because the present dispensation has a competitive information provision environment. Librarians also agreed that they know how to share information across their organizations, the finding also showed that librarians understand the needs of organizational members, and agreed that failure is applied as consideration to a better direction, the finding confirmed the study of Zhang and Xiangxia (2022) which revealed that organizational learning has a significant and positive influence on innovation performance. This result implies that in the university libraries in South-West, Nigeria, there seems to be a strong culture based on the prevailing indicators of mission, involvement, consistency and adaptability.

Research Question 3: What is the information technology used by librarians in university libraries in South-West, Nigeria?

Research question three sought to find out the information technology use of librarians in university libraries in South-west, Nigeria. The result outcomes revealed that librarians agreed

that they often use various information technology tools for various purposes. The finding is in line with the Technology Acceptance Model theory of Davis, *et al.* 1989 which opined that perceived usefulness is a factor to be considered before adopting any information technology. The finding also corroborated Zaellah, *et al.* (2019) study which revealed that information technology is used for various purposes such as sending and receiving information in the library.

Consequently, from the findings, librarians also agreed that they used information technology for various purposes, such as for better library practice, to meet the IT age demand, operational efficiency, flexibility and information search, the accuracy of library services, and for error-free services. These findings confirmed the Jonata *et al's* (2018), Aremua and Saka's (2018), Zaellah, *et al.* (2019) which revealed that information technology was used to enhance innovation performance, enhance accuracy, improve quality of information, reduce error, lessen administrative demand, used for library management and sourcing information, and transmitting the information.

The findings also showed that librarians agreed that they use some information technology tools in university libraries which include computers, electronic database ($\bar{x} = 3.70$), and smartphones, scanners, multiple projectors, and cameras. This finding is in line with Sahabi and Unobe (2021) who revealed that information technology tools comprised of internet, computers, radio, telephone, projectors, and television. However, computers and smartphones are used to a very high extent.

Conclusion

The study established that organizational culture and information technology use contribute to the practice of Evidence-based practice of librarians in universities in South-West, Nigeria. The study concluded that evidence-based practice cannot be achieved without recourse to a functional organizational culture and effective information technology use

Recommendations

The findings of this study necessitate certain recommendations that are of value for evidence-based practice improvement and sustainability in the university library systems. Hence, this study recommends the following:

1. State Governments in the South-West, university librarians, and professional librarians should enact innovative strategies toward improvements in evidence-based information practice in the dimensions of knowledge, skill, and practice.
2. Appropriate modalities should be put in place by university library management and librarians to monitor and evaluate librarians' knowledge as to curtail any shortcomings that could lead to low evidence-based practice activities in all sections of the university libraries.
3. University library management should always inculcate proactive improvement measures such as an enabling environment and standard policy across university library systems that will allow good organizational culture to thrive.
4. University library management and professional librarians should work together to overhaul the entire library system to ensure the adoption of Evidence-Based Practice in the library systems.
5. Appropriate policies should be introduced and implemented by library management and professional librarians in continuous training and retraining of librarians on evidence-based practice implementation and information technology use.

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